

METHODOLOGY FOR USING FOLK AND ACTIVITY GAMES IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION LESSONS

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Abstract: It is known that Uzbek folk games include games aimed at developing various physical qualities. Therefore, it is considered necessary to distinguish them according to their directions. Therefore, their classification (classification) takes the necessary place. In this regard, we believe that it would be appropriate to use Uzbek folk games in the middle of the lesson.

Key words: phylogenetics, classification, physical properties, outdoor games.

Active games are the main means of physical education. Active games creatively influence the physical development of children's motor activity, the formation of motor skills and physical qualities, and the promotion of health by increasing the functional activity of the body and enhancing the feeling of emotional joy.

The healing effect achieved by active games is inextricably linked with the positive emotions that arise during children's games and have a positive impact on the child's psyche. Emotional arousal awakens in children the desire to achieve a common goal for all and is expressed in a clear understanding of tasks, mutual compatibility of actions, precise targeting in space and playing conditions, and accelerated completion of tasks.

Based on children's strong passion and pleasant desire to achieve a goal, the role of will increases, helping to overcome various obstacles.

Motor games serve as a method of improving the motor skills acquired by children and training physical qualities.

During play, the child focuses on achieving the goal, and not on the method of performing the action. He acts according to the conditions of the game, showing dexterity and thereby improving his movements.

As a motor activity, motor play has certain characteristics: it requires the child to quickly react to signals and sudden changes in the game. Almost every action game has actions and movement cues for kids. For example, "sparrows and cars", "airplanes".

Active motor activity in the game trains the child's nervous system by improving the processes of excitation and inhibition, develops observation,

resourcefulness, the ability to find a goal in the environment, courage, dexterity, initiative, and choosing an independent path to achieve a goal.

Information about the origin and history of the games came to us through the book “Devon Lugotit Turk” by Mahmud Kashgari, the great Mingist, historian, ethnographer of the 11th century. The work presents examples of such game forms as challenge, collection, start of the game, throwing a checker, which are performed before the start of Uzbek outdoor games.

The work of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur “Baburnoma” also shows that fencing, wrestling and other sports have a great influence on the physical fitness of youth.

Children of the first age are brought up in families with the help of toys and fun games associated with the child’s first movements. In the lives of children older than this age, folk games with colorful combat content (including frame games, hirgoyi, and counting) occupy a large place. Starting from preschool age, in order to familiarize children with the customs, traditions and history of their people, the basic program “Child of the Third Millennium” defines national and outdoor games that are taught for each age group.

The famous teacher P. F. Lesgaft “considers play an exercise that helps prepare a child for life.” This exercise is an independent activity in which the child’s personal initiative is developed and moral qualities are cultivated. He says every game should have a purpose.

To do this, the activity in the game must correspond to the child’s ability to control himself; These movements should be mastered in advance through systematic exercises.

Regular participation in active games helps children develop control over their movements, regulate their body, that is, they learn to move under different tensions.

Games make the child very active, purposeful and quick in action; teaches you to follow the rules, behave well, and value friendship.

P. F. Lesgaft developed the theory of action games, and his followers developed it creatively. (E. A. Arkin, N. N. Kelko, T. I. Osokina).

T. Usmonkhodjaev, F. Khojaevlar, I. R. Abdurakhmanov, Sh. Galiev and others made a great contribution to the development of the theory of action games in Uzbekistan.

In his book “1001 Games,” T. Usmonkhodzhaev fully revealed the influence of active games on the child’s body and their significance. The book also clearly explains the content of action games suitable for preschool children, and the methodology for conducting them.

Active games are important in children's comprehensive education. Whatever the play activity is, the child likes it and evokes positive feelings in him. Outdoor games expand a child's worldview and are a unique means of understanding the environment.

The rules of outdoor games determine the course of the game, organize the motor activity of children, relationships, and contribute to the development of moral and volitional qualities.

It is important for every child to understand the rules of the game and be guided by the opinions of adults.

Through games, children develop such moral qualities as honesty, justice, friendship, courage, self-control, and determination.

In gaming activities, favorable conditions are created for the development of attention, perception, thinking, understanding and goal setting; houses help develop creative imagination, memory, intelligence, and mental activity. Thus, active games help the child's mental development.

Thanks to play activities, the child practically assimilates the reality of space and objects and at the same time significantly improves the mechanism of spatial perception.

For example, a child's independent choice of the direction of movement and his execution of movement in a direction strictly defined by the rules of the game require, on the one hand, a direct assessment of the game situation (directly perceived) and a visual-motor reaction (game actions), and on the other hand, sufficient understanding and representation of their actions in a spatial gaming environment.

Outdoor games form a simple time frame for children. They are expressed in the following: in understanding the sequence of game actions, first, then, further, earlier, all at the same time manifested in the rapid completion of game tasks at a signal, within the limits established for children. In these games, children practice aiming in space, sequence of actions and tracking them in time.

Independent explanation of the content of games, the entire game situation, its rules, the actions of the characters, indicating the location of children, game signs and directions of movement using spatial expressions, and evaluating the game played serves the mental development of children.

Active games provide comfort for the development of creative abilities in children of older kindergarten age. In this case, children can invent small games based on the content of the stories they hear. Action games are aesthetic activities in

their content and form. The variety of play actions is expressed in the fact that children perform them with obvious dexterity and original expression. The use of music in action games has great aesthetic value.

When conducting action games, we must not forget about the beauty and culture of actions: it is necessary to pay attention to children whose actions are to some extent expressive, to encourage those who are able to give expressive and successful images.

EDUCATIONAL VALUE OF THE ACTION GAME.

The first activity includes play, which plays a large role in the formation of personality. It is reflected in the impressions accumulated in children's games, strengthening and deepening their understanding of life events. Children, like adults, learn about the world through their activities. Teachers in our country note the great educational importance of outdoor games in preparing the younger generation for life, because the child develops through play.

The game enriches the senses, imagination and understanding of the participants. Our play teachers help the child develop holistically. They expand the concepts of his imagination, develop observation, intelligence, mental acuity, the ability to analyze, disseminate and popularize what he sees, on the basis of which he draws conclusions from events observed among others. Various sports are similar in the structure of movements (sports games, athletics, gymnastics, wrestling, swimming, etc.), and the game has educational value. Such games are aimed at consolidating and improving skills and previously learned technical and tactical techniques in a particular sport. Develops the ability to correctly assess spatial (local) and temporal relationships in gaming activities, quickly and correctly respond to the impact of a frequently changing situation in the game. Action games are very important for training the correct stereotypic action, because it is very difficult to correct it later. Outdoor games held locally in summer and winter conditions are of great educational importance: in children's camps, on trips, in recreation areas, on walks. Outdoor games help tourists, explorers, and explorers acquire the necessary educational skills.

Carrying out outdoor games with small objects (balls, bags, gymnastic sticks, flags) increases skin and muscle-motor sensitivity, helps improve motor functions of the hand and fingers, which is especially necessary for children of primary school and preschool age. In our country, introducing students to national folk games is of great educational importance. They introduce children to the culture of our people and their customs.

In outdoor games, game participants have to perform separate roles (game leader, secretary, referee, assistant referee, match organizer, etc.). This helps them develop organizational abilities and skills. Competitions in outdoor games introduce participants to the organization of competitions and the rules of the game. This knowledge and skills will help children compete on their own. If the teacher, educator, leader pays enough attention to this, then the educational aspect of the game will be enough.

EDUCATIONAL VALUE OF ACTION GAMES.

Motor games are very important in training physical qualities: speed, agility, strength, endurance, flexibility, at the same time, physical qualities are comprehensively developed in motor games.

Most action games require players to be fast (escape, chase, sound, react to visual cues in one second). The constantly changing situation in the game, which requires players to quickly move from one action to another, helps develop dexterity. Dynamic games develop strength. Games that require more effort and energy than vigorous effort develop endurance.

Games help develop the flexibility associated with frequent changes of direction.

Active games are very important in the spiritual education of a child. Outdoor games are called team games, and at the same time they teach children teamwork. The game develops in children a sense of camaraderie, mutual respect and responsibility for each other's actions. The child participates in a team game and sacrifices himself for the good of the team: he gives the ball to a friend who is in good condition, tries to save a friend who has been captured, and so on. In the game, they gradually learn to use each other's movements and feelings of friendship. From preschoolers to junior schoolchildren, the game only requires coordination of one's own actions with the actions of peers. Later in the game it will show using each other, helping each other. And finally, at the end of the game, the actions of their teams, their interest in their teams, and obedience will appear. A unique move in the game is one player versus one team versus another team. In this regard, players face various tasks that require timely solutions. To do this, you need to select another action and perform it in a short period of time. This helps the player to know his strength.

The exact interaction between players is determined not only by mutual cooperation and psychological adaptation, but also by the general nature of most game actions, the nature of fast execution and tension, and the severity of some experiences. The rules of the game help to cultivate conscious discipline, self-

control, the ability to “grab yourself” after strong excitement, a sudden impulse to gain the upper hand. Outdoor games also help teach children art and creativity. The first manifestation of creativity in children takes the form of play. In children's play, especially in children of preschool and primary school age, creative imagination plays an important role: a simple stick can be a horse, a bicycle, a gun and a sword. Develops the imagination of games in the form of a ball and organized games-actions with plot content. The influence of the situation around the game, the role of individual people in the imagination of children, understanding the course of events with distribution. role, children use their creative imagination when performing it. In the process of such games, creative imagination develops and improves. They help develop perception and perception, teach them to perceive the appearance of surrounding objects and all their interactions, learn about the environment and create new impressions in children, teach observation and logical thinking.

Musical games develop children's musical abilities. To develop children's musical abilities, the teacher uses the play method: games with movement to the sounds of music help to master musical forms and characters. In choral and musical games, the child shows his first ability to dance. In the game, the child learns all his personal qualities and characteristics. The manifestation of individual characteristics during play helps to get to know each child well and influences his development in the right direction. Only one activity, for example a game, does not fully reveal the student's personality traits. By its comprehensive nature, it will know whether the child is interested in the game or is interested in it. A child who does not interfere with other children in his class shows himself in a completely different way in the game. Since all this is extremely important, children need to be approached individually in the right way. Action games help improve certain qualities and skills necessary to pass the Alpomish and Barchina test standards.

National folk games, including Uzbek ones, like all folk inventions (music, pottery, carpet weaving tools, songs and dances, fairy tales, etc.), developed at various socio-economic stages of human history. They were invented and formed. based on specific ethno- and phylo-ontogenetic features.

In different regions of our republic, folk outdoor games have long been developed among different ages and segments of the population, but during the period of the White and Red Empires, the popularity of these games was extremely limited. After gaining independence, the games of the national movement began to be revived as the values of our nation, and now they have become not only a favorite pastime of our people, but are also included in the curricula of all educational institutions as a full-fledged subject. However, it should also be noted that the

scientific and methodological foundations of the national motor games of the people, their psychofunctional nature, significance and significance in the formation of physical qualities and sportsmanship have not yet been studied.

Currently, the undisclosed aspects of the national motor games discussed above, the study and implementation of problems associated with this area, are among the pressing issues in the physical education system of our country. Uzbek folk games arose from the unique traditions, living conditions, climate of residence, historical monuments and environmental conditions of the people and were used depending on their gender, age and health. But until now, most experts have not considered the possibility of isolating a separate classification (classification) and description (characteristics) of Uzbek folk games or have not paid enough attention to them. It should be noted that if such a classification and description had been given, then Uzbek folk games and action games in general would have been a great success. Because only knowing the classification and description of each game will it be possible to correctly determine the need and place of its use.

Games used in sporting events. The essence, content, significance of some folk games in education; Now we consider it appropriate to give examples of some folk games and clarify their essence, meaning and classification. The information of many other specialists highlights the results of the positive impact of folk games as a means of physical education, improving morality, oral speech, and developing sports skills.

In conclusion, it should be noted that students and young people need to carefully study the healing factors of nature and hygienic rules when organizing all classes, industrial training and sports events. Each specialist should help in their implementation with the conscious understanding that the measures, procedures and recommendations mentioned above are the key to health.

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